

Characterization and fully coupled numerical predictions of stealth composite with periodic patterns induced by artificial lightning strikes damage

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Introduction

Lightning strike (LS) protection for radar-absorbing composite

High electrical conductivity VS. Radar absorption properties

	Metal airframe	Conventional CFRP aircraft	Stealth composites aircraft
Electrical & thermal conductivity	Very High	High	Low
Lightning strike protection	O	△	X
EM wave absorption	X	X	O

Circuit analog absorber

- Circuit analog absorbers use patterned resistive sheets with specific sheet resistance and substrate as spacers

<Single layer circuit analog absorption material and its equivalent circuit map [1]>

<Fabricated periodic pattern coated glass fibers absorber[2]>

Protection concept for stealth composites against LS damage

< Configuration of DFRL, DFR and SFR[3]>

< Schematic of the foamed radar-absorbing sandwich composites with high-conductive film for lightning strike protection[3]>

Lightning strike test

<High current impulse generator and Lightning strike test setup >

Design and fabrication

Design and fabrication of stealth composites with PPS

Finite element model development

Flow chart of coupled thermal-electrical-structural model

<Flow chart of coupled thermal-electrical-structural model>

<(a) Lightning current waveform (Ipeak: 88 kA), and (b) boundary conditions of simulation>

Results and Discussion

Coupled thermal-electrical-structural analysis

- Non-destructive test was performed to determine the damaged area of the specimen following the lightning strike.
- The simulation predicted a damage area that was smaller than that observed experimentally.

<Temperature distribution of proposed PPS-based stealth composite (a) w/ LSP, (b) w/o LSP, (c) Thermal strain distribution of of proposed PPS-based stealth composite w/ LSP, and (d) temperature at the lightning strike point>

<(a) Overhead view of post-lightning PPS-based stealth composites, (b) damage area obtained using image processing (c) C-scan image (d) X-ray CT image >

Materials and methods

Manufacturing periodic pattern surface (PPS)

- The patterns were formed on polyimide film (PI film) by screen printing with conductive ink and silver paste.
- The sheet resistances of PPS and LSP were designed to be 150 ohm/sq and 0.45 ohm/sq.

<Schematic diagram of screen printing>

Principle of circuit analog absorber

<Circuit analog absorber and equivalent circuit[4]>

The input impedance (Z_{in}) of transmittance line with length d and short-circuit end is

$$Z_{in} = jZ_0 \tan kd \quad (1)$$

and overall impedance (Z) of R , C and L in series is

$$Z = R + \frac{1}{j\omega C} + j\omega L \quad (2)$$

and the input impedance in the starting end of the circuit (Z'_{in}) is

$$Z'_{in} = \frac{Z_{in}Z}{Z_{in} + Z} \quad (3)$$

then the reflectivity (Γ) of the whole circuit is

$$\Gamma = 20 \log \left| \frac{Z'_{in} - Z_0}{Z'_{in} + Z_0} \right| \quad (4)$$

in which Z_0 represents the is the characteristic impedance of free space

Conclusions and future works

- In this study, we propose radar absorbing structure using a periodic pattern surface for lightning strike protection.
- A coupled thermal-electrical-structural analysis, with lightning-strike experiments, was conducted to validate the proposed simulation model and assess its lightning protection performance.
- Although the thermal-electrical analysis was completed, comparison with the damage regions observed in the lightning-strike experiments revealed that the simulated damage areas were smaller.
- An analysis model incorporating matrix decomposition will be developed to perform a coupled thermal-electrical-structural analysis.

[1] W. Yongfeng et al. The research of circuit analog absorber using square resistance array. Progress in electromagnetic research symposium 2016.

[2] W-H Choi et al. Microwave absorbing structure using periodic pattern coated fabric. Composite Structures, 2020;238:111893.

[3] Woo-Hyeong Jang, Dongun Hong, Shingaram Malleth, Juhyeong Lee, Chaeyong Park, Chun-Gon Kim, Won-Ho Choi, Youngwoo Nam, Protection concept for foamed radar-absorbing sandwich composites with high-conductive film against lightning strike impacts, Composite Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, Volume 190, 2020, 108660.

[4] H-K Jang et al. Semi-cylindrical radar absorbing structures using fiber-reinforced composites and conducting polymers in the X-band. Advanced Composite Materials 2011;20:215-229.